

**COMPARATIVE QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF
PHYTOCHEMICALS OF THE LEAVES OF**

Carica papaya, Mangifera indica, and Cymbopogon citratus

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U2013/5545043

**A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
PLANT SCIENCE AND BIOTECHNOLOGY**

FACULTY OF SCIENCE

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RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA.

OCTOBER, 2018.

ABSTRACT

The research focused on the comparative examination of qualitative and quantitative presence of phytochemical constituents of *Carica papaya*, *Mangifera indica*, and *Cymbopogon citratus* leaves. The result of the methanolic and aqueous extracts of the leaves revealed the phytochemical contents for each plant as follows; Alkaloids (21.17%, 6.61% and 1.36%), saponins (0.51%, 7.49% and 1.18%), tannins (18.56%, 0.33% and 15.95%), flavonoid (29.60%, 11.74% and 8.59%), Trysin (0%, 2.15% and 0%), Phytate (0%,0.86% and 0%), Oxalate (0%, 2.02% and 0%), Glycoside (3.31%,0 and 0.61%), Phenol (19.15%,0 and 2.96%), Steroids (6.06%, 0 and 0), Quinines (4.68%,0% and 0%), Carotenoids (21.32%, 0%and 0%). The presence of these phytochemicals as indicated above disclose the scientific basis for the traditional uses of these plants both for medicine and food.The plants showed moderate to significant content of bioactive compounds, the potentials of which should be explored for use in the management and treatment of diseases. The potentials of each plant may vary as each plant exhibits different bioactive compounds and at different quantities as reflected in the values. However, more work needs to be done in order to ascertain which of these phyto-constituents has the greatest potency in exhibiting therapeutic or prophylactic value as well as to determine their use as alternative and effective approach in management and treatment of a number of existing and emerging diseases.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW.

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The issue of natural medicine is fast gaining ground all over the world (Amaechi, 2003). Despite controversies, pharmacists are coming to terms with natural medicine being an important aspect of health care delivery. The plant kingdom still holds many species of plants containing substances of medicinal value which are yet to be discovered (Nwankwo and Amaechi, 2013). Even though large numbers of plants are constantly being screened for their possible pharmacological value, it is estimated that only about 1% of Nigerian medicinal plants have been subjected to scientific evaluation for potential chemotherapeutic value (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012). The beneficial medicinal effects of plant materials typically results from the combination of secondary products present in the plant. To develop natural alternatives to existing synthetic chemical drugs, plants are being screened devotedly by scientist (Okwu *et al.*, 2017). This effort has brought about a practice called phytochemicals analysis.

These phytochemicals have either antioxidant or hormone like actions. Researchers are looking for specific compounds in these plants that may account for these healthful effects in humans (Craig, 1999).

Qualitative analysis simply means the quality of the chemical compounds formed during a plants natural metabolic process. Quantitative analysis simply means the degree of the presence of these secondary metabolites in the plants, presence of these phytochemicals is characterised (+) while absence is characterised (-).

The comparison could be between plants of different families, genera or species or between plants of the same backgrounds. Comparative quantitative and qualitative analyses studies are to check the parameters and relevance of plant extracts compared to the synthetic drugs, to encourage scientist in several plant chemical researches. This is important because nearly 50% of the drugs commonly used and prescribed are either derived from plants sources or contain chemical imitations of plant compounds (Ayodele, 2003). While the prolonged use of the remaining 50% synthetic can cause

damages to the body system (Okwu *et al.*, 2007), it is believed that the use of natural medicines do not have severe side effects.

1.2 PHYTOCHEMICALS

The term “phytochemicals” refers to a wide variety of chemical compounds produced by plants which may have effects on human health. They are naturally occurring biologically active compounds in plant, produced as a result of metabolic activities in plants hence (Vanisha and Hema, 2012). Phyto is a Greek word for plants, and chemical which means plant chemicals.

Each phytochemical comes from a variety of different plant sources and has different proposed effects and benefits for the human body (Vanisha and Hema, 2012). Kush *et al.* (2012) stated that phytochemicals are found in plant-based foods such as fruits, vegetables, beans and grains. They are promoted for the prevention and treatment of many health conditions, including cancer, heart disease, diabetes, and high blood pressure. They also act as anti-oxidants known to rid the body of harmful molecules known as free radicals, which can cause damage to a cell’s DNA. Much of the

evidence so far comes from the observation of cultures in which the diet comes mainly from plant source and which seems to have low rates of certain types of cancers, heart disease and obesity. For example the relatively low rates of breast and endometrial cancers and low obesity rate in some Asian cultures are credited, at least in parts, to dietary habits; while these cancers are more common in the United States because, the typical American diet is higher in fat and lower in fruits and vegetables, legumes and grains (Kushi *et al.*,2012). Phytochemicals act as natural defence system for host plants; they provide colours, aromas and flavours. Vegetables, herbs and spices contain very small quantities of wide range of volatile compounds which includes alcohols, ketones, aldehydes and terpenes (Elson and Yu, 1994). The most important of these phytochemicals also known as bioactive compounds, antioxidants or phytonutrients include alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins (Hill, 1952). Phytochemicals like phenols, carotenoids and isothiocyanates with antioxidant properties are used for augmenting cell mediated immune functions (Benedict, 1989).

1.3 TYPES OF PHYTOCHEMICAL

There are various types of phytochemical but the most common examples of phytochemicals include alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phytates and cyanogenic glycosides.

1.3.1 PHYTATE

Phytate is the salt form of phytic acid. It is also known as inositol hexakisphosphate or IP₆(Mullaney *et al.*, 2012). This acid is responsible for the storage of phosphorous in plant tissues, mainly found in bran, seeds and nuts. Catabolites of phytic acid are called lower inositol polyphosphates. Examples are inositol penta–(IP₅), tetra- (IP₄), and triphosphate – (IP₃), (Mullaney *et al.*, 2012).

When iron and zinc bind to phytic acid they form insoluble precipitates and are far less absorbable in the intestines. This process can therefore contribute to iron and zinc deficiencies in people whose intake is low such as those in developing countries. Contrary to that, one study correlated decreased osteoporosis risk with phytic acid consumption. It acts as an acid, chelating the vitamin niacin, the deficiency of which is

known as pellagra. In this regard, it is an anti-nutrient, despite its possible therapeutic effects (Mullaney *et al.*,2012).

1.3.2 SAPONINS

These are a group of chemicals with detergent-like properties that plants produce –to help them resist microbial pathogens such as fungi (Akubugwoand Ugbogu, 2007).

Saponins are a structurally diverse class of compounds occurring in many plant species. They are traditionally divided into triterpenoid, spirostanoil and furostanolsaponins (Grenby, 1991).

They are generally known as volatile, surface active compouds that are widely distributed in nature occurring primarily in the plant kingdom (Lasztity *et al.*, 1998).

The name ‘saponin’ is derived from the Latin word Sapo, which means ‘soap’ because it forms soap-like foams when shaken with water. Saponins are steroid glycosides or triterpenes. They have diverse range of properties which include sweetness and bitterness (Grenby, 1991); foaming and emulsifying properties (Price *et al.* 1987).

Pharmacological and medicinal properties (Attele *et al.*, 1999), haemolytic properties (Oda *et al.*, 2000) as well as antimicrobial, insecticidal and molluscidal activities (Sparg *et al.*, 2004).

1.3.4 CYANOGENIC GLYCOSIDES

Cyanogenic glycosides are composed of a-Hydroxynitrile type aglycone and of a sugar moiety (mostly D-glucose). The number of cyanogenic glycosides (CG) containing taxa is at least 2,500 and a lot of such belongs to families Fabaceae, Rosaceae, Linaceae, Compositae and others (Harborn, 1973). The production of HCN depends on both the biosynthesis of CGS and the existence (or absence) of its degrading enzymes. The generation of HCN from CGS is a two-step process involving a deglycosylation and a cleavage of the molecules regulated by B-glycosidase and a-hydroxynitrilase (Harborn, 1973). Cyanogenesis is the ability of some plants to synthesize cyanogenic glycosides which when enzymically hydrolysed, release cyanohydric acid (HCN) known as prussic acid (Harborn, 1973). In the intact plant the enzyme and cyanogenic glycoside remain separated, but when the plant tissue is damaged both come in contact

and cyanohydric acid is released (Bell, 1981). Cyanohydric acid is extremely toxic to a wide spectrum of organisms due to its ability to link with metals (Fe^{++} , Mn^{++} and Cu^{++}) that are functional groups of many enzymes, inhibitory process like the reduction of oxygen in the cytochrome respiratory chain, electron transport in the photosynthesis and the activity of enzymes like catalase and oxidase (Cheeke, 1995).

Cyanogenesis is one of the mechanisms that can serve as a protective device against predators such as herbivores. The level of cyanogenic glycosides produced is dependent upon the age, variety of plant and environmental factors (Cooper-Driver and Swain, 1976).

1.3.5 TANNINS

Tannins are complex organic, non-nitrogenous plant products which generally have astringent properties (Egunyomiet *al.*, 2009). In Asia (Japanese and Chinese) natural healing, the tannin containing plant extract are used as astringents against diarrhoea, as diuretics, against stomach and duodenal tumours, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antioxidant and haemostatic pharmaceuticals. Tannins are used in the dyestuff industry

as caustic dyes (tannin dyes) and in production of inks (iron gallate ink). In food industry, tannins are used to clarify wine, beer and fruit juices also they are used as antioxidants. They are used as coagulants in rubber production. From chemical point of view, it is difficult to define tannins as the term encompasses some very diverse oligomers and polymers (De Bruyne *et al.*, 1999).

The term tannin was first used by Seguin in 1796 to denote substances which have ability to combine with animal hides and convert them into leather, a process known as tanning of the hide (Nwogu *et al.*, 2008).

1.3.6 ALKALOIDS

Alkaloids are naturally occurring products that contain nitrogen bases or atoms. The name alkaloid is derived from the 'alkaline' which are basic in character.

Alkaloids are naturally synthesized by a large number of organisms such as animals, plants, bacteria and fungi. Alkaloids have bitter taste and are used as local anaesthetics and stimulants as cocaine (Moorachain, 2000). Alkaloids are significant for the protection and survival of plants because they ensure their survival against micro-

organisms (antibacterial and antifungal activities), insects and herbivores (feeding deterrents) and also against other plants by means of allelopathically active chemicals (Hamburger *et al.*, 1991). Alkaloids have many pharmacological activities including anti-hypertensive effects (many indole alkaloids), anti-arrhythmic effects (quinidine, sparteine), antimalarial activity (quinine), and anticancer actions (dimeric indoles, vincristine, and vinblastine). Some alkaloids have stimulant property as caffeine and nicotine, morphine are used as analgesics and quinine as antimalarial drug (Akunyili, 2003).

1.3.7 FLAVONOIDS

Flavonoids are polyphenolic compounds that are ubiquitous in nature. More than 4000 flavonoids have been recognised, many of which occur in vegetables, fruits and beverages like tea, coffee, and fruit drinks (Gibson *et al.*, 1998). Flavonoids occur in vascular plants as aglycones, glycosides and methylated derivatives. Approximately 650 flavones and 1030 flavonols are known. Small amounts of aglycones (i.e. flavonoids without attached sugar) are often present and represent the important

proportion of the total flavonoid compounds in the plants (Harvey, 2000). Flavonoids have broad biological and pharmacological activities including antimicrobial, oestrogenic activity, anti-allergic, anti-oxidant, vascular activity, cytotoxicity, anti-inflammatory as well as anti-tumor activities but the best described property of almost every group of flavonoids is their ability to act as powerful antioxidant which can protect the human body against free radicals and reactive oxygen species (American Cancer Society, 2000).

1.4 MEDICINAL PLANTS

Medicinal plants are plants used to relieve, prevent or cure a disease (Arias, 1999). In these plants one or more of their organs contain substances which are precursors for the synthesis of useful drugs (Sofowora, 1982), these plants are also considered important sources of nutrition.

The term herbals became very common in Western culture focusing on the idea of using plants for medicinal purposes. (Rasool, 2012).

1.4.1 *MANGIFERA INDICA L.*

Mangifera indica L. (mango) is known as “the king of fruits” because it is the most popular fruit in the tropical regions. It is the national fruit of India and the Philippines, and the national tree of Bangladesh (Usman, *et al.*, 2001). The word mango is derived from the Tamil word “Mangkay or Man-gay”. The mango belongs to genus *Mangifera*, which consists of numerous species of tropical fruits in the family of *Anacardiaceae* (Kostermans, *et al.*, 1993.). *Mangifera indica* L. is native to India and Southeast Asia, where it has been cultivated for over 4000 years for the good qualities of the fruits. Currently, mango is also grown in Central America (Blancas *et al.*, 2015), Africa (Khakimov *et al.*, 2016), Australia (San, *et al.*, 2017) and for a few years in Europe (Rodríguez and Dayalan, 2012). Over one thousand mango fruit varieties are available worldwide, although only a few are produced on a commercial scale. In the Mediterranean area, Spain and Israel are the major producing countries. The species was introduced to East-Asia around 400-500 Bc from India, next in the 15th century to Philippines and then in the 16th century to Africa and Brazil by the Portuguese, cultivated varieties have been introduced to other warm regions of the world. Encyclopaedia of Life and Integrated Taxonomic System (ITIS), 2015, reported that

about 180 different cultivars are cultivated around the world. The many varieties of mango are a result of genetic improvement practices. The species was described for science by Linnaeus in 1753.

Mango was introduced in Nigeria towards the end of 19th century. The government of southern Nigeria received some mango cultivars from the Botanical Gardens of Jamaica in 1898, Adejoh (1980). These were planted at the then Botanical gardens of old Calabar. These cultivars spread to other parts of Nigeria and became highly adapted to Nigerian condition.

In Nigeria today, mango (*Mangifera indica*) represents one of the most popular fruits that is cultivated among her citizens. The varieties cultivated in Nigeria have been classified into these popularly known varieties: Alphonso, Amelia, Apple Haden, Kent, Ruby, Julie.

1.4.2 COMMON NAMES OF MANGOES IN THE NIGERIAN MARKET

In Nigeria, there are many varieties of mango trees often distinguished by their fruit characteristics and are therefore assigned common names based on these characteristics. The common names given to some variety are Big-no-fibre, Small-fibre, kerosene mango, Julie, German, Opioro, Normal (Ogbomosho/ Enugu (Eastern)/ Calabar/ Abuja). The challenge therefore remains with lack of accurately named germplasm and cultivars. This is a major limitation on the effective study and communication regarding the general biology among the cultivars. Common names are generally misleading, confusing and universally unacceptable (Aguoru,2009; International Code for Botanical Nomenclature, 2015).

1.4.3 *CARICA PAPAYA*

Carica Linn. (Caricaceae) is a genus of rapid growing unbranched small trees, native to tropical America and widely distributed in the tropics. About four varieties are found, of which *Carica papaya*, Linn. "Papaya" is the most widely.

1.4.3.2 Distribution

The tree has gained importance as a plantation crop in Australia, Hawaii, the Philippines, India, Sri Lanka, South Africa and a number of other countries in tropical America and South-Eastern Asia. Papaya was introduced into India in the 16th century and was naturalized quickly. It is a quick growing and heavy yielding crop and is grown both commercially and in home gardens.

1.4.5 CYMBOPOGON CITRATUS.

The genus *Cymbopogon* comprises 140 species that are widely distributed in the world. Approximately 45 species have been reported to occur in India (Sugumaran *et al.*, 2005). *Cymbopogon citratus* Known as West Indian lemon grass is an important species of Poaceae family commonly found in Southeast Asia. Its origin can be tracked to India, It is a tall, clumped perennial grass growing to a height of 1 m and it is the commonly growing grass in Kodaikanal hills, Tamil Nadu. The leaf blade is linear, tapered at both ends and can grow to a length of 50 cm and width of 1.5 cm (Sugumaran *et al.*, 2005). The plant is commonly used in folk medicine in many countries since it exhibits antioxidant properties which in turn inhibits the propagation of free radical reactions and protects the human body from disease. The isolated and

identified substances from the leaves are mainly aldehydes, alkaloids, saponins, terpenes, alcohols, ketones, flavonoids and these components have various medicinal properties. The chemical composition of the essential oil and aqueous extracts of *C. citratus* varies according to the geographical origin (Gomes *et al.*, 2007). Kodaikanal is situated on top of palani hills and always cool (18-22°C) throughout the year due to high elevation of the city (2,200m). In the present investigation qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analyses will be carried out using lemongrass leaves grown in Abia state.

1.5 AIM OF STUDY

The present study is targeted at evaluating the various types of phytochemicals present in the leaves of three plant species; *Mangifera indica*, *Carica papaya* and *Cymbopogon citratus* which are medicinal plants grown in Rivers state.

1.6 STUDY OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Ascertain the common phytochemicals in the leaves of *Mangifera indica* (mango), *Carica papaya* (pawpaw) and *Cymbopogon citratus*.
2. Isolate and identify the functional components of *Mangifera indica* (mango), *Carica papaya* (pawpaw) and *Cymbopogon citratus* leaves.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1.7.1 DESCRIPTION OF *MANGIFERA INDICA*.

Tree is medium to large (10-40 m in height), evergreen with symmetrical, rounded canopy ranging from low and dense to upright and open. Bark is usually dark grey-brown to black, rather smooth, superficially cracked or inconspicuously fissured, peeling off in irregular, rather thick pieces. The tree forms a long unbranched long tap root (up to 6-8 m and more) plus a dense mass of superficial feeder roots. Effective root system of an 18- year old mango tree may reach a 1.2 m depth with lateral spread as far as 7.5m (Bojappa *et al.*, 1974). The leaves are simple alternately arranged, 15-45 cm in length. The petiole varies in length from 1 to 12 cm, always swollen at the base. Leaves are variable in shapes like oval-lanceolate, lanceolate, oblong, linear-oblong, ovate, obovate-lanceolate or roundish-oblong (Sing, 1960). The upper surface is shining and dark green while the lower is glabrous light green. Hermaphrodite and male flowers are produced in the same panicle, usually with a larger number of the later. The size of both male and hermaphrodite flowers varies from 6 to 8 mm in diameter. They are sub-sessile, rarely pedicellate, and have a sweet smell. The pollen grains are of variable shapes, with the size varying from 20 to 35 micron (Mukherjee

et al., 1950). The fruit is more or less compressed, fleshy drupe, varies considerably in size, shape, colour, presence of fibre, flavour, taste and several other characters.

1.7.2 FLOWERS

Tiny (1/8 - 1/4), red-yellow flowers are borne in large, terminal panicles of up to 400 individuals. About 25%-98% of the flowers are male, depending on cultivar and the remaining are hermaphroditic. Panicles are initiated in terminal buds 1-3 months prior to flowering, triggered by low temperatures or seasonally dry conditions.

1.7.3 POLLINATION

Mangoes are considered self-fertile and do not require pollinates, but research indicates that some cultivars are self-unfruitful or at least benefits from cross-pollination. Fruit set is generally just a few percent, with an average of only one mango borne per panicle. Pollination is achieved by wild insects, and to a lesser extent, honey bees.

1.7.4 FRUIT

Mango fruit is a drupe. The large, flattened, kidney-shaped central seed contains starchy embryo, and constitutes 20% of fruit weight. The skin has yellow or green background colour, with red/orange bluish in many cultivars, and thicker than usual for drupaceous fruits. The skin contains irritating oils, particularly in unripe fruits(Bojappa *et al.*, 1974).

1.7.5 CONTRIBUTION TO DIET

Mangoes are one of the finest fresh fruits in the world, but can be dried, pickled or cooked as well(Bojappa *et al.*, 1974). Mangoes are higher in vitamin C than citrus fruits. Green mangoes are the tropical equivalent of green apples-tart, crisp, and somewhat dry, often eaten with salt. They are cooked or used in salads in the tropics. About 25% of mangoes are processed into juices, chutneys, or dried. The large seed can be processed into flour, and the fat it contains can be extracted and substituted for cocoa butter. (Per capita consumption of mango is 2.1lbs/year.)

TABLE 1.1 DEITARY VALUE, PER 100G EDIBLE PORTION.

NUTRIENT COMPOSITION	CONTENT %
Water	80
Calories	63
Protein	0.4
Fat	0.4
Carbohydrate	16
Crude Fibre	1.0
VITAMINES	% of US RDA*
Vitamin A	20
Thiamine, B1	3.6
Riboflavin, B2	2.5

Niacin	2.2
Vitamin. C	200
Calcium	1.1
Phosphorus	1.5
Iron	4.0
Sodium	-
Potassium	-

(% of recommended daily allowance seed FDA, assuming a 154lb male adult = 2700 calories per day).

1.8 SOIL AND CLIMATE

1. SOILS:

Adequately drained and mildly acidic (pH 6-7)

2. CLIMATE:

Climate zones of lowland tropics or forest-free subtropical areas cease growth at temp. Below 55-60°C (not truly dormant). Leaves and fruit are injured by mild frost, (28-32°C).

1.9.1 TAXONOMICAL CLASSIFICATION OF *Mangifera indica*.

1. Kingdom: Plantae
2. Subkingdom: Tracheobionta
3. Superdivision: Spermatophyta
4. Division: Magnoliophyta
5. Class: Magnoliopsida
6. Subclass: Rosidae
7. Order: Sapindales
8. Family: Anacardiaceae
9. Genus: *Mangifera*
10. Species: *Mangifera. Indica*

1.9.2. CULTIVARS:

In mango orchards several cultivars are usually inter-bred to improve cross-pollination. Many *Mangifera indica* cultivars were derived from chanced seedlings.

There are two classes of cultivars

- Indochinese:

The mangos of the Indochinese group are described as flattened, kidney-shaped, and oblong with light green or yellow skin and little or no red colour. The Indochinese cultivars usually have a poly-embryonic seed, and most are resistant to Anthracnose, the major fungal disease affecting mango.

- Indian:

The Indian class is characterized by mangos that are more plump and rounded, and that have a bright red blotch on the skin. Indians mangos have mono-embryonic seed that facilitates breeding efforts, and are commonly susceptible to anthracnose.

1.10.1 PHYTOCHEMICALS FOUND IN *MAGNIFERA INDICA*

Alkaloids

Alkaloids are basic nitrogenous compounds with definite physiological and pharmacological activity. Alkaloids are natural plant compounds having basic characteristics and containing at least one nitrogen atom in a heterocyclic chain. Alkaloids are usually colourless, crystalline, non-volatile solid which are insoluble in water, but are soluble in ethanol. Other forms of alkaloids have been identified as liquids like cocaine and nicotine which are soluble in water (Finar, 1993). Most alkaloids are precipitates from neutral or slightly acidic solution by Meyer's reagent (Evans, 2002). Alkaloids are chemical constituent from plants that can act or have effect on the nervous system of human body and are used as analgesics because they are capable of relieving pains. They have bactericidal and antispasmodic effects and can be used to achieve the same effect when given in the natural state, (Ganellin and Rosert, 1993). Many alkaloids are toxic to other organism, they often have pharmacological effects used as medication, as recreation drugs examples are local

stimulant caffeine, cocaine and nicotine (Robert *et al.*, 2006). Although alkaloids act on a diversity of metabolic systems in human and other animal, they almost uniformly invoke a bitter taste. Extracts from plants containing toxic alkaloids such as Aconitine and tubocurarine have been used since antiquity for poisoning of arrow, (Rhoades and David, 1979).

TANNINS

Tannins are heterogeneous group of complex compounds widely distributed in plants (Okwu, 2005). They are abundant in leaves and in many unripe fruits. They are divided into two groups, namely; hydrolyzed and condensed tannins. Hydrolysable tannins are based on gallic acid, usually as multiple esters with D-glucose, while the numerous condensed tannins (often pro-anthocyanides) are derived from flavonoid monomers (Harborne, 1973; Okwu, 2005). Many physiological activities such as stimulation of phagocytic cells, host mediated tumour activity and wide range of anti-infective action have been assigned to tannins (Okwu, 2005). Studies have shown that tannins decrease protein quality by reducing digestibility and palatability. It causes

damage to the intestinal tract and interferes with absorption of iron and possibly lead to carcinogenic effect. Tannin is used in tannin hides converting them to leather or other medicinal purposes. They are characterized by a property known as astringent (Harborne, 1973). They also play a role in protection and are used as pesticides in plant growth regulation. Tannin have been traditionally considered anti-nutritional but it is now known that their beneficial or anti-nutritional properties depend on their chemical structure and dosage.

FLAVONOID

Flavonoids are 15-carbon compounds generally distributed throughout the plant kingdom. They are known to be synthesized by plants in response to microbial infection and have been found in vitro to be effective against a wide array of microorganisms. (Harborne, 1973). Flavones with the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$ is commonly found in plant flavonoid (Martindale, 1996). Flavonoids are potent water soluble super antioxidants and free radical scavengers which prevent oxidative cell damage, they have strong anti-cancer activity and protects against all stages of cancer.

Flavonoids in the body are known to reduce the risk of heart diseases (Urquiaga and Leighton, 2000). In terms of anti-cancer activity, they inhibit the initiation, promotion and progression of tumours (Urquiaga and Leighton 2000, Okwu, 2005). In recent times, plant flavonoids have attracted attention as potential important dietary cancer chemo-protective agents. Some iso-flavones act as allelochemicals widely used in insecticides (Kandaswami *et al.*, 1994).

SAPONINS

Saponins are group of naturally occurring oily glycoside that foam freely when shaken with water. They occur in a wide variety of plants including acacia, soapwort, soap root etc. saponins have been and sometimes still used as cleaning agents and as foam producers, notably in fire extinguishing fluids. They have a bitter taste and when ingested orally are practically non-poisonous to warm blooded animals. When ingested directly into the blood stream, however, they are dangerous and quickly dissolve red blood cells. Hydrolysis of a saponin brought about by acids or by enzymes give a sugar (often but not necessarily glucose) and sapogenin, the latter

being either a triterpene or a steroid. Some sugars and saponins are useful as raw materials for synthesis of steroid hormones (Iyengar, 1995).

PHENOLS

Phenols are plant secondary metabolite spread throughout the plant kingdom. They are class of natural organic compounds which are essential for the growth and reproduction of plants and are produced as a response for defending injured plants against pathogens. They have been the subject of great number of biological, chemical agricultural and medicinal studies. Phenolic acid may occur in food as esters or glycosides conjugated with other natural compounds such as flavonoids, alcohols and sterols. Some phenols are germicidal and are used in formulating disinfectants. Phenols are aromatic chemical compounds with weakly acidic properties and are characterized by a Hydroxyl (OH) group attached directly to an aromatic ring. The presence of phenols is considered to be potentially toxic to the growth and development of pathogens in plants (Okwu, 2005). Poly-phenols might interfere in several steps that lead to the development of malignant tumours, it may play a role in

inactivating carcinogens and inhibiting the expression of mutagens (Urquiaga and Leighton, 2000; Okwu, 2005).

1.10.2 ETHNO-MEDICINAL USES.

Various parts of mango are used for more than thousands of years as wide variety of ethno-medicinal use:

Roots and Bark:

They are used as astringent, acrid, refrigerant, styptic, anti-syphilitic, vulnerary, anti-emetic, anti-inflammatory and constipating. They are useful in vitiated conditions of pitta, metrorrhagia, calorrhagia, pneumorrhagia, leucorrhoea, syphilis, uteritis, wounds, ulcer and vomiting. The juice of fresh bark has a marked action on mucous membranes, in menorrhoea, leucorrhoca, bleeding piles and diarrhoea(Akunyili, 2013).

Leaves:

Used as astringent. They are also useful in vitiated conditions of cough, hiccup, hyperdipsia, burning sensation, hemorrhages, haemoptysis, haemorrhoids, wounds, ulcers, diarrhoea, dysentery, pharyngopathy, Scorpion sting and stomachopathy. The ash of burnt leaves are useful in burns and scalds. The smoke from burning leaves is inhaled for relief of throat diseases (Okwu, 2006).

Flowers:

They are used as astringent, refrigerant, styptic, vulnerary, constipating and haematinic. The dried flowers are useful in vitiated conditions of pitta, haemorrhages, haemoptysis, wounds, ulcers, anorexia, dyspepsia, catarrh of bladder, diarrhoea, chronic dysentery and anemia (Akunyili, 2013).

Fruits:

The unripe fruits are acidic, acrid, antiscorbutic, refrigerant, digestive and carminative. They are useful in dysentery ophthalmia, eruptions, urethrorrhoea and vaginopathy.

The ripe fruits are refrigerant, sweet, emollient, laxative, cardiogenic, haemostatic, aphrodisiac, and tonic. They are also used in vitiated conditions vata and pitta, anorexia, dyspepsia, cardiopathy, haemoptysis, haemorrhages from uterus, lungs and intestine, emaciation, and anemia.

Seed:

The seed kernel is rich source of protein (8.5%) and Gallic acid (Akunyili, 2013). It is sweet, acrid, astringent, refrigerant, anthelmintic, constipating, haemostatic, vulnerary and uterine tonic. It is useful in vitiated conditions of pitta and cough, helminthiasis, chronic diarrhea, dysentery, haemorrhages, haemoptysis, haemorrhoids, ulcers, bruises, leucorrhoea, menorrhagia, diabetes, heat burn and vomiting.

1.10.3 PHARMACOLOGICAL USES INCLUDES:

Anti-cancer, Anti-diabetic, Anti-inflammatory, Hepatoprotective, Anti-hemorrhagic, Anti-tetanus, **Analgesic and Antipyretic**, Anti-ulcer, Anti-diarrheal, **Antibacterial**, **Antifungal**, **Antimalarial**, Immunoregulation, Cardio protective, Laxative:

1.11 *Caricapapaya*

1.11.2 *Carica papaya* L.

Common name: papaya, pawpaw, melon tree (English) papayier, arbredemelon (French) papaya, gedang (Indonesia) papaya, betexkatalah (Malaysia) malakor, loko, makuaithet (Thailand). Papaya have always held an attraction for people; there is a great economic importance to tropical regions where it is widely grown for its edible fruit and latex. *Carica papaya*, a small group of trees with their leaves in the terminal clusters and latex vessels throughout their tissue. There are about 40 species of the genus *Carica* the American tropics and subtropics and papaya originated in Southern Mexico and Central America. The early Spanish and Portuguese explorers carried it to the Caribbean and South East Asia during the Spanish exploration in the 16th Century. It distributed rapidly to India, Oceania, Africa, and today it is grown throughout the tropical and warmer subtropical areas of the world (Morton, 1977; Hartman *et al.*, 1981).

1.11.3 Botanical Descriptions

Stem

Carica papaya is a fast-growing tree herbaceous like plant 5-7 meters in height. Papaya normally has a mono-axial stem without branching but it has multi-stems when damaged. When the stem is wounded white milky latex oozed from the wound. Although papaya can be up to 9 meters height, it is easily damaged and makes harvesting of fruit difficult (Nakasone & Paull, 1998).

Leaves

Leaves, clustered around the apex of trunk and branches, have nearly cylindrical stalks, hollow, green, purple-streaked or deep-purple, 10 to 40 in. (25 to 100 cm) long; the leaf blade has 7 to 11 main and some secondary, irregular, pointed lobes and prominent veins; leaf surface is yellow-green to dark green above, paler beneath. Usually male and female flowers are born on separate plants, but hermaphrodite (bisexual) flower often occur; and a male plant convert to a female after beheading.

Flower

Papaya flowers are born inflorescences which appear in the axils of leaves. It can be female, male or hermaphrodite flowers. Female flowers are held close against the stem as single flowers or in cluster of 2-3 flowers. Male flowers are smaller and more numerous. Hermaphrodite (perfect) flowers are intermediate between the female and male (Nakasone & Paull 1998). Flowers emerge singly or in clusters from the main stem among the lower leaves, the female short-stalked, and the male with drooping peduncles 10 to 40 in. (25 to 100 cm) long. Corolla is 1/2 to 1 in. (1.25 to 2.5 cm) long, with 5 oblong, re-ocurred white petals.

Fruit is extremely variable in shape and size according to variety; it may be nearly round, pear-shaped, oval or oblong; that of wild plants may be as small as a hen's egg, white, in cultivation the fruit ranges from 5 in. (12.5 cm) to 2 ft. (60 cm) in length and up to 8 in. (20 cm) thick.

The fruit's skin is smooth, relatively thin, deep yellow to orange or salmon-red, sweet and more or less musky. The central cavity of the fruit is lined with a dry, pulpy

membrane to which adhere with numerous black, rough, peppery seeds, each with a glistening, transparent, gelatinous coating (Williams, 1975; Brouk, 1975; Cogley, 1976; Morton, 1977).

1.11.4 *Carica papaya* Taxonomy

Carica papaya L. Belongs to the family of Caricaceae and is dicotyledonous Polygamous (Having male and Female flower on the same plant). The genus *Carica* is derived from the Latin name for a kind of fig which the leaves and fruits of *Carica* resemble, the specific epithet *papaya* probably comes from the common name for the fruit (Du-Puy and Telford 1993). Caricaceae comprises 31 species in three genera (*Carica*, *Jacaratia* and *Jarilla*), from tropical America and one genus, *Cylicomorpha*, from equatorial Africa (Nakasone and Paull 1998).

1.11.5 Taxonomical Classification

1. Kingdom: Plantae
2. Subkingdom: Viridiplantae
3. Superdivision: Embryophyta

4. Division: Tracheophyta

5. Class: Magnoliopsida

6. Superorder: Rosanae

7. Order: Brassicales

8. Family: Caricaceae

9. Genus: *Carica*

10. Species: *C. papaya*

1.11.6 CONTRIBUTION TO DIET

TABLE 1.2 NUTRIENT COMPOSITION OF PAPAYA PER 100 GRAMS.

NUTRIENT COMPOSITION	COMPOSITION/100grams
Energy	59.0Kcal
Moisture	84.4%
Protein	1.0g
Fat	0.1g
Carbohydrate	13.5g

Fibre	0.5g
Ash	0.5g
Vitamin B1	0.08g
Vitamin B2	0.15mg
Ascorbic acid	69.3mg

Source: Agri-Food Business Development Centre.2015

1.11.7 ETHNOMEDICINAL USES

Various parts of the plant have been used in traditional medicine in different parts of the world. The efficacy of treatment with *C. papaya* is dependent on the quantity of the different compounds in the preparation. The quantity of the compound is also different in the fruit, latex, leaves and roots and varies with the extraction method, age of plant part, and the cultivation and sex of tree (Morton, 1977). In West and Central Africa, the fruit extracts are used by traditional healers for the treatment of hypertension and for the prevention of miscarriages in women (personal

communication), and is known to produce uterine relaxation in the rat. In the Northern Nigeria, a cold water decoction of the ripe fruit is used to control and calm mentally agitated individuals (Gupta *et al.*, 1990). The unripe papaya has been shown to have antimicrobial and antioxidant activities (Osato *et al.*, 1993). Moreover, the methanol extract of unripened fruit markedly depressed the blood pressure and heart rate in rats.

1.11.8 PHARMACOLOGICAL USES

Many reports have shown the pharmacological properties of papaya latex with anthelmintic activity, antifungal action and bacteriostatic effects on a number of infectious organisms (Giordani *et al.*, 1991; Satrija *et al.*, 1994; Cherian, 2000). The latex has many applications in folk medicine. It is used as a styptic and vermifuge, an anti-chigger application and remedy for freckles, warts, corns, ringworm, infected wounds, malignant tumours and the pain of burns. Small doses of latex and sugar are taken as a digestive, emmenagogue and for whooping cough. In India and Malaya, the latex is smeared on the mouth of the uterus to induce abortion (reviewed by Morton, 1977). Cherian (2000) has shown that the crude papaya latex contains an

uterotonic principle which can evoke sustained contraction of the uterus. Crushed leaves and seeds have been used for anthelmintic purpose and fever. In Ibolnd and Ghaha, the yellow red of the dried leaves is used to treat gastric problems (see reviewed by Gupta *et al.*, 1990). Intraperitoneal injection of alcoholic extract of papaya leaf was shown to be effective as sedative, central muscle relaxation and anti-convulsant property in rat (Gupta *et al.*, 1990). Papaya seeds are used against intestinal parasite in humans and farm animals in India, Central and South America and elsewhere. The extracts of papaya seeds have been shown to be effective against helminthes *in vitro* and in infected animals (reviewed by Wilson *et al.*, 2002). Studies with the chloroform, alcoholic and benzene extract of papaya seeds have shown their antifertility effects in male rats, mice and rabbits. The reversal of fertility occurred within 15 days to a month, and the compound was free of side effect (Lohiya *et al.*, 2000). Furthermore, the pentane extracts of papaya seed caused relaxation of mammalian vascular smooth muscle (Wilson *et al.*, 2002). Sripanidkulchai *et al.*, (2001) reported that the decoction of papaya root is employed by practitioners of Northeast of Thailand for treatment of dysuria. A similar extract also showed diuretic

activity in rats. The diuretic activity of *Carica. Papaya* may be due to the high salt content of its extract (Sripanidkulchai *et al.*, 2001).

Toxicity

The fresh latex is acrid and can cause severe eye inflammation. It can provoke irritation and blisters if it is allowed to remain in contact with skin. Papaya harvesters should wear gloves and aprons or overalls to avoid dermatitis, the latex will digest the tissue and cause sores. Internally, it is a severe gastric irritant and has been employed in malicious poisoning. Some people are acutely allergic to parts of the papaya plant such as, its pollen, fruit and latex. Particularly, sensitive persons react to meat tenderized by papain administration in any form or manner as medication. Pharmacists may experience rhinitis, asthma and other allergic reactions from handling papain preparations (Morton, 1977).

Chemistry

As discussed earlier, *C. papaya* contains many biologically active compounds, the level of compounds varies in fruit, latex, seed, leave and root. In addition, plant parts

from male and female tree, or the cultivation can also cause a variation in quantity of compounds (Morton, 1977). Apart from nutritional substances, many biologically active compounds in *C. papaya* have been reported.

Papaya leaves contain glycoside, carposide, and alkaloids (will be discussed later). Fresh leaves latex contains 75% water, 4.5% caouchouc-like substance, 7% pectinous matter and salts, 0.44% malic acid, 5.3% papain, 2.4% fat and 2.9% resin.

The fatty oil of seeds contains 16.97 saturated acids (11.3% palmitic, 5.25% steraric and 0.31% arachicic), 78.63% unsaturated acids (76.5% oleic and 2.13% linoleic). The seeds, air-dried, yield 660- 760 mg/100 g of bactericidal aglycone of glucotropaeolin benzyl isothiocyante (BITC), a glycoside, sinigrin, the enzyme myrosin and carpasemine (Morton, 1977).

1.12 *Cymbopogon citratus*

Cymbopogon citratus commonly known as lemon grass is a perennial, aromatic C4 grass.

Habit: perennial, caespitose. Rhizomes short. Culms 100-200 cm long. Ligule and ciliate membrane. Leaf-blades tapering towards sheath, 45-90cm long 10-20 mm wide, aromatic.

1.12.2 TAXONOMY

Cymbopogon is a very large genus within the grass family Poaceae, consisting of over 500 species that grows in the tropical and sub-tropical regions from mountains to grass lands to arid zones, including the species *Cymbopogon Citratus* and *Cymbopogon Flexuosus*. *Cymbopogon* species are aromatic and are produce commercially important oils, including citronella.

1.12.3 TAXONOMIC CLASSIFICATION

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Spermatophyta

Subphylum: Angiospermae

Class: Monocotyledonae

Order: cyperales

Family: Poaceae

Genus: *Cymbopogon*

Species: *Cymbopogon citratus*

1.12.4PHYTOCHEMICAL AND MINERAL CONTENTS

Many biological active substances has been isolated and elucidated in *Cymbopogon citratus*, this includes tannins, carbohydrates, flavonoids, glycosides, alkaloids, steroids. And the isolated mineral isolated from *Cymbopogon* includes vitamin C, iron, potassium, calcium, manganese, zinc etc, (Jasha, 2014).

1.12.5ETHNOMEDICINAL USES

Lemon grass is one of the most popular plant medicines in Nigeria, where it is used for treating several disorders such as:

- I. Nervous disorders

- II. Stomach problems (stomach-aches, diarrhoea, gas bowel spasms, vomiting)
- III. Fever
- IV. Flu
- V. Back-pain
- VI. Sciatica
- VII. Sprains
- VIII. Rheumatism
- IX. Menstrual disorders etc.

1.12.6 PHARMACOLOGICAL USES

The essential oil extracted from aromatic plants in medicine was used since 16th century. Cobley (1956), Gildemeister and Hoffmann (1956), reported that the chemical composition of the essential oils of *Cymbopogon* may vary from one species to another species. But the chemical composition of lemongrass oils extracted from *C. pendulus*, *C. citratus* and *C. flexuosus* are almost identical. Aretander (1960), Han *et al.*

(1971), Fodaet *al.* (1975) and Guenther (1980), studied the essential oils of *Cymbopogon* species and its relevance to the industry.

Several pharmacological activities been reported for essential oil of lemon grass includes analgesic, antidepressant, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antipyretic, antiseptic, astringent, bactericidal, galactagogue, insecticidal, nervine, sedative, anti-cancer.

CHAPTER TWO

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection of plant materials

Leaves of *Cymbopogon citratus* were collected from Sipele water side in Oyigbo LGA of Rivers State, while the leaves of *Carica papaya* and *Mangifera indica* were collected from University of Port Harcourt bottling plant.

2.2 Chemicals and reagents

All the chemicals and reagents used in the study were of analytical grade and were products of British Drug House laboratory, England.

2.3 Sample preparation

The leaves were washed under running tap water to remove the surface pollutants, they were then cut into small pieces and sun dried for 14 days. The samples were ground into powder and stored each in an air tight bottle prior to use for analysis.

PLATE 1.1: Fresh *Mangifera indica* leaves.

PLATE 1.2: Dried *Mangifera indica* leaves.

PLATE 1.3: Grounded samples of *Mangifera indica* bottled in an air tight container.

PLATE 2.1: Fresh leaves of *Carica papaya*.

PLATE 2.2: Dried leaves of *Carica papaya*.

PLATE 2.3: Grounded samples of *Carica papaya* bottled in an air tight container.

PLATE 3.1: Fresh leaves of *Cymbopogon citratus*.

PLATE 3.2: Dried leaves of *Cymbopogon citratus*.

PLATE 3.3: Grounded samples of *Cymbopogon citratus* bottled in an air tight container.

2.4 Phytochemical analysis.

The analysis for the phytochemical contents of the plant samples were carried out according to standard methods (Sofowara, 1993; AOAC 2000).

Test for Alkaloids

0.5ml of each leaf extract were dissolved in 5ml of 1% HCl in steam bath in different conical flask, 6 drops of Dragendorff's reagent were added to the dissolved leaf extracts. Precipitate or turbidity indicated the presence of alkaloids.

Test for Flavanoids

1 ml of the leaves extract were dissolved in 5 ml of diluted ammonia, 1ml of conc. sulphuric acid was added. Appearance of yellow colour indicates the presence of flavanoids.

Test for Tannins

2 ml of leaf filtrate obtained by boiling 0.5 gm leaf and 20 ml of water, 2 drops of FeCl_3 were added to each samples and the presence of tannins was confirmed on observation of a blue or black precipitate.

Test for Saponins

50 mg of the dried leaf samples was diluted with distilled water, 20 ml. Frothing test was done by pouring the suspension in a graduated cylinder and shaken for 3 minutes. The formation of 2 cm foam and its persistence indicates the presence of saponins.

Test for Cardiac Glycosides

The presence of cardiac glycosides was confirmed by Keller-Kilani test which is performed by the addition of 1 ml glacial acetic acid, 1 drop of 1% FeCl_3 and 2ml of conc. sulphuric acid were added to 2 ml of each of the leaf filtrate resulting in the appearance of green blue colour.

Test for Phenols

50 mg of the leave powders were each dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water. A few drops of neutral FeCl_3 solution were added and the appearance of dark green colour indicated the presence of phenols.

Test for Quinine:

2 drops of alcoholic KOH was added to 1ml of each leave extract.

Test for Oxalates

3 drops of 80% H_2SO_4 were added to 0.5 g of the extracts. The formation of bright crystal disappeared on the addition of reagents which confirmed the presence of oxalate in calcium oxalate form.

Test Phytate

Phytate was determined by the methods of Early and DeTurk (1944) by colorimetric method in absorption at 420 nm. The solution used contained 1.2% HCl and 10% Na_2SO_4 and 0.6% HCl containing 5% Na_2SO_4 , 3 ml of sulfuric and 3 ml of nitric acid.

Test for Carotenoid

5 g of leaves was crushed followed by addition of 10 ml of acetone and the mixture was filtered. The extract obtained was transferred to a separating funnel which contained 20 ml of petroleum ether. The acetone was removed by slowly adding distilled water and the procedure was repeated until no residual solvent remained. The

extract was then transferred to a flask and 5 g of anhydrous sodium sulfate was added. Using petroleum ether the volume was made up and the samples were read at 450 nm.

Test for Steroids:

1ml of methanolic extract was added to 1ml of chloroform, 2-3ml of acetic anhydride and 2 drops of conc. H_2SO_4 were also added to the plant samples. Rosy red colour, indicated the presence of steroids

Test for Trypsin

0.2g of each sample was weighed into a screw-cap centrifuge tube. 10ml of 0.1M phosphate buffer was added and the contents were shaken at room temperature for 1h on a UDY shaker. The suspension obtained was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5min and filtered through filter paper. The volume of each was adjusted to 2ml with phosphate buffer. The test tubes were placed in water bath, maintained at 37°C and 6ml of 5% tricarboxylic acid (TCA) solution was added to all the tubes previously kept at 37°C and were incubated for 20min. the reaction was stopped after 20min by adding 6ml of TCA solution to the experimental tubes and then shaken. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 1hr at room temperature. The mixture was filtered using filter paper and

the absorbance of filtrate from sample and trypsin standard solutions were read at 280nm.

2.5 Quantitative Determination

To determine the quantity of each of the constituents, 2g of each powdered sample was first defatted with 100ml of diethyl-ether for 2hours using a soxhlet apparatus.

2.5 Sterilization of Glass Wares

All glass ware used in this research work were washed with detergent, rinse with distilled water and air dried. They were also sterilized on a hot air oven and each material was wrapped with Aluminium foil before sterilization.

CHAPTER THREE

RESULTS

3.1 QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF THREE PLANT SAMPLES (*Carica papaya*, *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Mangifera indica*).

Carica papaya showed the highest amount of Alkaloids and Flavonoids and Phenol; it was the only sample that contained Carotenoid. *Mangifera indica* had the highest amount of saponin; it was seen to contain trypsin, phytate and oxalate. *Cymbopogon citratus* was high in Tannin while low in Alkaloids, Saponins, Flavonoid, Trypsin, Glycoside, and Phenol etc. Results of presence and amount of phytochemical in these plants are summarised in Table 3.1. Details of the contents for each plant are shown in Figs 3.1 to 3.3. Comparing the occurrence of these chemicals in each plant is shown in Fig 3.4.

Table 3.1: Phytochemical composition of the leaves of *Carica papaya*, *Mangifera indica*, and *Cymbopogon citratus* (%).

PARAMETERS	<i>Carica papaya</i>	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>
Alkaloids	21.17	6.61	1.36
Tannins	18.56	0.33	15.95
Saponins	0.51	7.49	1.18
Flavonoid	29.60	11.74	8.59
Trysin	-	2.15	-
Phytate	-	0.86	-
Oxalate	-	2.02	-
Glycoside	3.31	-	0.61
Phenol	19.15	-	2.96
Steroids	6.06	-	-
Quinines	4.68	-	-
Carotenoids	21.32	-	-

FIG 3.1: Result for Phytochemical content (%) in *Carica papaya* leaf.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS of *Mangifera indica*

FIG 3.2: Result for Phytochemical content (%) in *Mangifera indica* leaf.

FIG 3.3: Result for Phytochemical content (%) in *Cymbopogon citratus* leaf.

FIG 3.4: Variations in percentage of the phytochemical contents in the leaves of *Carica papaya*, *Mangifera indica* and *Cymbopogon citratus* respectively.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

4.1 DISCUSSION

It has been widely observed and accepted that the medicinal value of plants lies in the bioactive phyto-components present in the plant (Arinola, & Dania, 2011). In this study several biochemical constituents of three medicinal plants were evaluated, the result of phytochemicals in the investigation showed the presence of biochemical constituents such as alkaloids, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, tannins etc, extracted quantitatively and qualitatively. Table 3.1 shows the result of qualitative and quantitative analysis which reveals the presence and quantity of these chemical substances. This study shows the presence of different phytochemicals compounds that can be of valuable therapeutic activity.

The phytochemical analysis showed that phytate, oxalate, trysin which are anti-nutrients were only contained in mango. Alkaloid was higher in pawpaw while lemon grass and pawpaw had higher percentage of tannin respectively (FAO, 1980). Saponin

was highest in mango. Flavonoid was very high in pawpaw followed by mango and lemon grass. Although phytate and oxalate can bind calcium, magnesium, iron and zinc making them unavailable, but their levels were not high in mango. saponin was higher in mango than the rest. Alkaloids, tannins and saponins have been reported to have medicinal properties. The presence of these phytochemical constituents showed that the three varieties have medicinal property. (Sofowora, 1993) reported the roles of these phytochemicals as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-hypertensive and anti-microbial. Saponins and tannins also exhibit cytotoxic effects and growth inhibition making them suitable as tumor inhibiting agents (Akindahunsi & Salawu, 2005, Asl & Hossein, 2008).

Tannins are dietary anti-nutrients that are responsible for the astringent taste of foods and drinks (Chikezie *et al.*, 2008). Tannins bind to both proteins and carbohydrates which has several implications for commodities containing tannins. Their presence can cause browning or other pigmentation problems in both fresh foods and processed products. The presence of tannin in the plants implies they may have astringent properties and in addition, could quicken the healing of wounds and burns (Farquar,

1996). This justifies their usage in herbal medicine. Pawpaw and mango leaves had higher percentage tannin contents while lemon grass had the least.

Saponin has the property of precipitating and coagulating red blood cells. Some of the characteristics of saponins include formation of foams in aqueous solutions, hemolytic activity, cholesterol binding properties (Eleazu *et al.*, 2010) and bitterness (Sodipo *et al.*, 2000). The saponin contents of pawpaw and lemon grass were observed not to differ much from each other (0.51, 1.18) respectively. The percentage composition of saponin in mango was the highest among the plants studied. The moderate amounts of saponin in all the plants investigated suggested that they may not be deleterious to the user.

Alkaloids are basic natural products occurring primarily in plants. They occur as one or more heterocyclic nitrogen atoms and are generally found in the form of salts with organic acids. Alkaloids are the most efficient therapeutically significant plant substances. Pure isolated alkaloids and their synthetic derivatives are used as basic medicinal agents because of their analgesic, antispasmodic and anti-bacterial properties (Eleazu *et al.*, 2011). The alkaloid content of pawpaw was significantly

higher than in other plants that were studied while that of lemon grass was the least. The high alkaloid contents of all the plants investigated justify the therapeutic use of these plants.

The large amounts of flavonoids in all the plants investigated infer that the plants have biological functions such as protection against allergies, inflammation, free radical, platelet aggregation, microbes, ulcers, hepatoxins, viruses and tumor (Okwu, 2004). Flavonoids are potent water soluble antioxidants and free radical scavengers which prevent oxidative cell damage, have strong anticancer activity and protect against the different levels of carcinogenesis (Okwu, 2004). Flavonoids in the intestine lower the risk of heart diseases. The antioxidant potentials of plants have been linked with their flavonoids contents. In addition, the therapeutic potentials of plants have been linked with their antioxidant potentials (Akinmalodun *et al.*, 2007, and Eleazu *et al.*, 2011). As antioxidants, the flavonoids from these plants may provide anti-inflammatory activity. Thus the high alkaloid and flavonoid contents of these plants explain their therapeutic use in herbal medicine especially in the treatment of wounds, burns and ulcers.

Glucosides are compounds that yield glucose, hydrogen cyanide and aldehyde or ketone upon hydrolysis with an acid or enzyme. Dietary exposure to cyanide occurs mainly in the consumption of food stuffs rich in endogeneous cyanide in the form of cyanogenic glucosides. This cyanide could be lethal as it intercalates with cytochrome oxidase for aerobic function (Bolhius, 1954). Only free cyanide (CN⁻) is toxic and if hydrolysis does not occur, the glycoside remains stable and the food using this product becomes safe.

Values obtained for all plant samples investigated were below the lethal dose for man (Bolhius, 1954) indicating the safety in the therapeutic usage of these plants. (Table 1)

Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between the total phytochemical contents among the different plant extracts. The pawpaw extract was found to have the highest total of phenolic, flavonoid alkaloid, tannin and caroteinoid amounts, while lemon grass presented the lowest contents ($p < 0.05$) of flavonoid and alkaloid compound.

4.2

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study showed the presence of significant phytochemicals in the test plants and the quantities available through solvent extraction revealed that all the plants possess pharmacological active chemicals. All the different species of plant leaves that were assayed contained significant quantities of saponin, only mango contained oxalate, phytate glycoside though in moderate levels suggesting that they may not be deleterious to the user. They were also observed to contain high quantities of alkaloids and flavonoids suggesting their antioxidant potentials and justifying their therapeutic uses which could be utilized in drug formulation. The plants showed moderate to significant antioxidant activity as well as free radical scavenging potentials which may be explored for usage in the management and treatment of diseases, although the potentials of each plant may vary as each plant exhibits different bioactive compounds and at different quantities as reflected in the values (Table 3.1). The low quantities of tannin in all the plants studied suggest that usage of these plants in herbal medicine can neither interfere with dietary iron absorption nor inhibit digestive enzymes.

However, more work needs to be done in order to ascertain which of these phyto-constituents has the greatest potency in exhibiting therapeutic or prophylactic value as well as further researches to determine the constituent responsible for the antioxidant activities of the plants because these medicinal plants, especially in Africa, may lead to alternative and effective approach in management and treatment of a number of existing and emerging diseases.

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APPENDICES

ANOVA SUMMARY FOR PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE LEAVES OF *Carica papaya*, *Mangifera indica*, and *Cymbopogon citratus*

ANOVA FOR PHYTOCHEMICALS

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
21.17	8	103.19	12.89875	111.5312
6.61	6	24.59	4.098333	20.54022
1.36	5	29.29	5.858	41.78397

ANOVA

<i>Source of</i>						
<i>Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between						
Groups	304.908	2	152.454	2.32188	0.130212	3.633723
Within						
Groups	1050.556	16	65.65973			
Total	1355.464	18				